

Relationship of insulin, blood glucose, and our body cells

Pancreas locates at the back of your stomach. Pancreas produces insulin.

Insulin is like a key. Glucose is in the blood, and it needs to go into the body cells through the bloodstream, through the little veins. Insulin has to be there with it to unlock the cell's door and allow glucose to go in. Insulin opens the door to allow glucose from the blood into the body cells.

If there is not enough insulin, the glucose cannot go into the cells. The glucose will stay in the blood. This means that the body cells get no energy.

When too much glucose is left in the blood, it is dangerous to our body. This is what happening to a diabetic person.

Pancreas locates at the back of your stomach.

Storyboard 1: Pancreas locates at the back of your stomach.

Storyboard 2: Pancreas produces insulin. Insulin is like a key.

Glucose is in the blood

Glucose is in the blood

Glucose is in the blood

Glucose is in the blood

Storyboards 3, 4, 5, and 6: Glucose is in the blood

and it needs to go into the body cells through the blood stream, through the little veins.

Storyboard 7: and it needs to go into the body cells through the bloodstream, through the little veins.

Insulin has to be there with it to unlock the cell's door

Storyboards 8 and 9: Insulin has to be there with it to unlock the cell's door and allow glucose to go in.

Storyboard 10: If there is not enough insulin, the glucose cannot go into the cells. The glucose will stay in the blood. This means that the body cells get no energy.

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